

Review Article

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Happiness is the New Rich

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Abstract As a child is born it is taught that only way to prove ones worth is by being successful. The entire focus is on success and not happiness. The human mind is thus trained from the time it starts comprehension to be competitive. Unfortunately the definition of success is translated solely into material success and financial gains. Thus unknowingly humans are taught to be competitors and they forget to appreciate the good in others and to feel happy for others, hence most of the times people are unhappy not because they lack anything but because people around them have more. They fail to realize that financial gains are not the parameters to determine how happy a person is in life. Someone may be on the zenith of their career and yet unhappy with life yet on the other hand people living in stark depravity might still be happier. The majoritarian utilitarian populace has blurred the society’s vision and obfuscated the entire purpose of human existence. The ultimate purpose that man was created was to do good and be good or in other words to be happy. There were no career goals or materialistic pursuits prescribed for him. As the civilizations progressed the physical comforts and pomp and show took predominance over the sole purpose of human life which is to be happy. This paper is an attempt to reassess the purpose of human life and focus on what can make life more meaningful and fulfilling leading to ultimate happiness.

Keywords Success, happiness, purpose, aim, life.

1. Introduction

The world is full of stories about successful people. The books promising success sell fast in the book store racks. There are unending talks about victories, so many quotes about winning:

“Winning takes precedence over all. There’s no gray area. No almos. (Kobe Bryant)

“For me, winning isn’t something that happens suddenly on the field when the whistle blows and the crowds roar. Winning is something that builds physically and mentally every day that you train and every night that you dream”(Emmitt Smith)

“No matter how much you’ve won, no matter how many games, no matter how many championships, no matter how many Super Bowls, you’re not winning now, so you stink.” (Bill Parcells)

“All I cared about in tennis was winning.” (Pete Sampras)

“Winning solves everything.” (Tiger Woods)

“I’m a mad dog whose only concern is winning.” (Charles Barkley)

“For nothing can seem foul to those that win.” (Shakespeare, King Henry IV)

Does it then imply that life is a perennial battle and the purpose of our being born is to strive forever? If this be the case then the vital question is what is to be conquered. This puzzle needs to be solved so that the much coveted success after which we are trained to run after right from the childhood does not become pyrrhic in the end.

2. Method

The behaviour of individuals from both the extremely financially settled background and those with paucity of financial resources was closely studied. Their reaction to good weather and leisure time was studied. On the one hand was a group of people from renowned and successful business houses of Udaipur city. On the other hand was a group of people who earned their livelihood through menial tasks. Their behaviour was studied on a pleasant evening, on Sundays, at late evening. It was observed that the little joys of life were lost on the people with no financial struggle. They languished in cribbing about the bad behaviour of others towards them. A constant complain of this group was how people didn't act according to their expectations. The main cause of their sorrow seemed to be their entitled attitude and lack of drive to see through their own shortcomings. The other group although lived under severe financial burden was keen to savour whatever joy things around them had to offer. They laughed even at the silliest jokes. Some of them jubilated so much that at times it made one wonder what made them laugh so much. The hubbub of their lives didn't leave them with the time to complain much about the behaviour of others. Their worries were for physical necessities which left them with less complains for those around them.

3. Results and Discussion

Though the resources for luxury as well as the sources of income are increasing by the minute, so is the growing discontent. The many cases of homicide and genocide are proof enough to implicate this. In order to find the answers to these impending questions it is perhaps time to do some serious rethinking over the parameters of success and yardsticks defining victory and happiness.

This leads us to the basic question: What is the real motive of human existence? Was such a complex being made up of such complex structure of nerves and tendons with such an intricate morphology created by God for nothing? To help us understand the modus operandi of human creation it is apt that we seek the help of mythology because where logic fails theology steps in to guide the way. Every religion states that the sole aim of human life is happiness. Let us take Christianity as a case study. God created Adam and Eve. The ideal abode Paradise was created solely for them. The sole purpose of their creation till Satan lured them with his sweet talks, was to be happy. If it is denied in the present life than it is promised in the afterlife to coax humans to do good. Some may call it Moksha, others may call it jannat or heaven.

So does it then implicate that the success of human existence is validated as long as we are able to be happy. However though all happy people are successful not all successful people are happy. Though a comfortable lifestyle and a good financial condition is inevitable for a happy state of existence yet it is a fact that material comfort alone does not the guarantee happiness. So then what is the perfect recipe for success that will result in happiness? The key to happiness lies in spending the precious life energy into constructive action. It is utilizing individual capabilities to the best of ones potential. You ran hard in a race but did not win. You tried your best but did not get the desired outcome. So are you a loser? Is it being UNSUCCESSFUL? The real defeat would have been not to try. If you'd not given your best. Rejoice in the fact that the winner had a chance to win because numerous others participated. Be happy that you tried because tomorrow maybe you won't even be in the situation to give it another try

Rather than focusing on such competitive terms as winners and failures the sole aim of one's life should be to excel: to be a better version of yourself than you were yesterday. To be excelsior does not mean waiting for grand opportunities to prove your worth. Satisfaction derived out of the mundane tasks performed diligently too can lead to a sense of well-being leading straight to happiness. You baked a cake it turned out perfect and you excel. Someone is mean to you. You are unaffected by it with it you excel. People may mock at you yet you don't lose focus you excel. The sole attempt to outdo what we did yesterday is to be excelsior. Not everybody will be lucky enough to participate in a grand historical event. But we can contribute our small share in making the world a happy place by doing whatever comes our way with utmost honesty, dedication and perseverance thus canonizing the ordinary to the extraordinary. When you set your competition against yourself you are no longer in competition with anyone else. Slowly and gradually as you practise the skill of ameliorating yourself the negative forces of the outside world stop having any impact on your existence. It no longer matters who is above or below you because you are not a part of that rat race any more. You become your own light.

Cultivating a hobby can be extremely instrumental in seeking that inner light. A hobby practiced everyday can serve as the sponge that absorbs all the failings and frustrations of any tedious day. As important it is to engross the mind in a hobby equally important it is to overcome the urge to talk about our miseries. Talking about the bad experience is otiose as it does not change anything but only makes an episode stronger in the mind. It is like overlooking the entire page of good in life and staring on a grief that is but a speck on the page. Isn't it ingratitude towards God who has blessed us with even those things (To be born as a human tops the list) that we did not even ask for? When thankfulness becomes a habit life becomes a constant celebration. When positive approach to life becomes a way of life happiness exudes, radiating not only ones whole being but everyone who come in contact with such a person.

4. Conclusion

The actual contentment on life depends more on realizing that happiness is a decision which has to be constantly practised. Knowing yourself is the first step towards attaining this goal. By realizing the transience of human life we have to constantly strive to develop the inner strength and beauty of the existence so that in the business of taking care of the physical comforts we do not forget that all human efforts are ultimately a drive to be happy.

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